

Accessible Workflows for Collecting & Preserving Human Rights Video Evidence

No Time to Wait Symposium
London, 26 Oct 2018

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WITNESS trains and equips human rights defenders around the world to use **video and technology** to expose abuses and fight for **justice** and lasting **change**.

Accessible Workflows for Collecting & Preserving Human Rights Video Evidence

- Human rights video evidence examples
- WITNESS collaborations
 - Community documentation of police violence in the US
 - Social media documenting state violence against Rohingya in Burma
- Gaps / needs

Video evidence example: DRC military tribunal

Collect Verifiable Photos and Videos

How the eyeWitness app allows your photos and/or video footage to be stored in a virtual evidence locker for use in trials and investigations

Source, Eyewitness to Atrocities, <https://www.eyewitnessproject.org/>

Video evidence example: Walter Scott case

Ex-South Carolina cop Michael Slager gets 20 years for Walter Scott killing

By [Meridith Edwards](#) and [Dakin Andone](#), CNN

🕒 Updated 2110 GMT (0510 HKT) December 7, 2017

SCOTT FAMILY PHOTOGRAPHY/SCOTT FAMILY PHOTOGRAPHY/SCOTT FAMILY PHOTOGRAPHY

News & buzz

First lady's office calls out T.I. for 'disgusting' video...

For the first time, a woman is leading the largest command in...

Video evidence example: War crimes arrest warrant

Source: <https://www.bellingcat.com/news/mena/2017/09/04/geolocating-libyas-social-media-executioner/>

Source: Bellingcat: How a Werfalli Execution Site Was Geolocated,
<https://www.bellingcat.com/news/mena/2017/10/03/how-an-execution-site-was-geolocated/>

Projects

- **Profiling the Police:** Archiving community documentation of police misconduct in the US.

**BERKELEY
COPWATCH**

- **Rohingya Genocide Archive:** Archiving social media of state violence against Rohingya in Burma.

Profiling the Police

Profiling the Police

CHARGES DROPPED AGAINST BROOKLYN FRUIT VENDOR WHOSE ARREST WAS CAUGHT ON VIDEO

By NY1 News | February 14, 2015 @5:11 AM

SHARE

Charges against a Sunset Park fruit vendor whose arrest was caught on video have been dropped.

Archiving El Grito's video collection

1. Planning.
2. Collecting /selecting videos.
3. Capturing miniDV tapes.
4. Processing and ingesting video files to storage.
5. Description, developing basic cataloging scheme.
6. Using videos and other public information to create officer timelines.

El Grito - Collection planning

SEE IT WITNESS FILM IT CHANGE IT

NAME

Planning Workbook: Police Violence Video Database
El Grito de Sunset Park Use Case

Process at a Glance

- Plan**
Defining Need, Establishing Scope, Collection Plan
- Archive**
Digitize, Verify, Preserve, Develop Metadata Schema
- Analyze**
Analysis, Visualization, Creating Context and Narrative
- Share**
Release Findings & Curation Toolkit

About this Workbook

This workbook was developed by WITNESS and El Grito de Sunset Park, a community-based organization in Brooklyn, to share our learnings and suggested basic practices for organizing, preserving and analyzing large collections of police violence videos. This guidance stems from our collaborative project, *Profiling the Police* (elgrito.witness.org).

The workbook walks you step-by-step through the process of planning, archiving, and gleaning data from video collections of police abuse documentation. It includes worksheets and guidance on specific issues such as defining your project, ethics, consent and security. It also offers examples of how we addressed these issues in our project.

Collection Policy Worksheet page 3 of 5

Will you collect older videotape formats?

Keep in mind that videotapes are obsolete and need to be digitized or re-formatted to digital files. Do you have the capacity to digitize the videotape formats you intend to collect?

Any specific document formats collected or not collected? Will you be collecting any other types of files or documentation? (e.g. .jpeg, .doc, .pdf, .mp3, physical documents)

Does the collection only include unique materials that do not exist elsewhere (i.e. original recordings), or non-unique materials (e.g. news clips, videos downloaded from other groups, etc.) also?

Does the collection only include material that can be traced to a source and verified, or does it include material whose provenance is unknown and whose content is unverified?

Planning Workbook
<https://elgrito.witness.org/>

El Grito - Pre-ingest

El Grito - Ingest and Description

EXACTLY
(BAGIT)

+

ERD

FileMaker
An Apple Subsidiary

- Advocacy information
- Sample officer timeline
- Workflow toolkit

Denying the Right to Record

El Grito video captured a number of incidents of officers routinely mistating or interfering with the community's right to record police activity.

Watch the full playlist

NYPD Lieutenant McNeil, 72nd Precinct, lying on camera saying it's...

"Members of the service will not interfere with the videotaping or the photographing of incidents in public places. Intentional interference such as blocking or obstructing cameras or harassing the photographer constitutes censorship."

NYPD PATROL GUIDE
Section 212-49

SOURCE: NYPD Patrol Guide

VIDEO DATA MODELING ENTITIES ATTRIBUTES RELATIONSHIPS DATA MODEL TEST METADATA SCHEMA

El Grito de Sunset Park Use Case

METADATA INTRODUCTION

WHAT IS THIS?

Metadata is essential because it makes it possible to identify, find, understand and analyze video. For example, knowing where a video was shot, when, and by whom, is extremely important for understanding the video content. Without metadata, you might not be able to authenticate a video, or to recognize the importance of a piece of footage (and without technical metadata, your video player won't even know how to play the video!)

This page outlines the steps we took to collect and create metadata for the El Grito project. The following pages outline the steps we then took to turn the information structure that emerged from our work into a reusable data model.

WHY DO THIS?

Metadata is key to any curation or archiving project.

Metadata literally means "data about data." In this case, our "data" is video, so metadata is any information that describes the video. Metadata can include descriptive, technical, structural, and administrative types of information.

Part 2: Berkeley Copwatch database

- Started in 1990, co-founded by Andrea Prichett.
- Regular copwatch patrols, Peoples' Investigations, Know Your Rights trainings, UC Berkeley DeCal class.

**BERKELEY
COPWATCH**

Berkeley Copwatch database project

- Clarifying video collection policy.
- Re-design database with end uses in mind, with more structure, and better documentation.
- Streamlining video ingest workflows from camera --> storage, and input to database.

Where we're at now

COLLABORATIVE WORKFLOW DOCUMENTATION

ocofs [DRAFT] #
Shared with WITNESS + 10

Berkeley Copwatch Database Intake Protocols [DRAFT]

Back to >Table of Contents Version 1.0

(original document from Andrea)

Principles for intake: WHY do we collect footage?

- **INDIVIDUAL SUPPORT:** We want to curate footage and archive information to help people to manage their cases and find support for their cases. We want to support people knowing where to take their footage and assessing what they want to do with it. If we do not upload the footage because it has incriminating information or other reasons, we will make every effort to refer them to lawyers/advocates/ etc...who can assist them.
- **REVIEW OF PATTERNS AND PRACTICES:** We want to gather and distribute and analyze information pertaining to the conduct of individual officers as well as the policies and practices of a department.
- **EVIDENCE IN CLASS ACTION LAWSUITS:** We may have campaigns where we specifically seek particular information and categorize the footage on that basis (events).
- **EARLY WARNING:** We want to be able to warn the city leaders when an officer has a disproportionate number of offenses and we need to be assigned and directed to mental

Create Incident Records

Create a new Incident record

<https://www.dropbox.com/s/68619x8sqsb2gq3/Incident-1.mov?dl=0>

- Click + **New Incident** button to create a new database record for the incident.
- Enter:
 - Date (mm/dd/yyyy)
 - Time (hh:mm AM or PM)
 - Location - street address or intersection or place name.
 - Neighborhood - TPD - this field has been set up, but no neighborhoods have been defined

How to Offload Footage After a Copwatch Shift

Follow the steps below for guidance on creating a new shift folder, offloading footage from your Camcorder, iPhone or Android and importing it onto the computer. Also learn how to link the video to an Incident Record in the Database.

A. Setting Up Your Shift Folder

Organize all shift videos by Date > Camera A and Camera B + Shift Report

1. Open 'Shifts' folder on external media drive 'BCW Media Drive (ca. 2018)

2. Highlight the 'mm.dd.yyyy.' folder and press 'Command+C' to copy Folder then press 'Command+V' to create a copy

3. Rename 'mm.dd.yyyy.' to date of your shift
4. Rename 'MM.DD.YYYY_Shift Report' after entering shift information into it

Rohingya Genocide Archive

- Working with a Rohingya organization in SE Asia to establish sustainable Rohingya-led archive.
- Collect and preserve video and social media documentation of genocide and crimes against humanity against Rohingya people for purposes of investigation, accountability, justice, and truth-telling.

Background

- Rohingya people - marginalized and persecuted stateless minority in Burma.
- Numerous crackdowns by military using horrific violence, including on 25 Aug 2017 “clearance operation”.
- Major humanitarian crisis - thousands killed, missing; 700,000 Rohingya have fled.
- UN Fact Finding Mission recommends investigation and prosecution of Burmese military for crimes against humanity, war crimes and genocide.
- Preliminary examination at ICC underway on Rohingya forced deportation to Bangladesh.

Facebook bans Rohingya group's posts as minority faces 'ethnic cleansing'

As hundreds of thousands flee a brutal campaign by the Myanmar military, the social media company labels an insurgent group a 'dangerous organization'

▲ More than 400,000 Rohingya Muslims have fled Myanmar. Photograph: Zuma Wire/Rex/Shutterstock

Amid international accusations that Myanmar's military is engaging in "ethnic cleansing" of the Rohingya Muslim minority, Facebook designated a

Inside Facebook's Myanmar operation

Hatebook

A REUTERS SPECIAL REPORT

of communal violence in Myanmar. In March, a United Nations investigator said Facebook had been used to incite hatred against the Rohingya. REUTERS

Why Facebook is losing the war on hate speech in Myanmar

Reuters found more than 1,000 examples of posts, comments and pornographic images attacking the Rohingya and other Muslims on Facebook. A secretive operation set up by the social media giant to combat the hate speech is failing to end the problem.

M.
@YoursRohingya

Follow

3pm 28/8/2017: #Rohingya villagers flee from #AlayThanKyaw as #ArsonAttacks & Killings by #Myanmar army army by going house to house growing

YouTube

Search

A group of Rakhine set fire two Rohingya houses in TatMinChaung Village, #Buthidaung 23rd Nov
755 views

49 2 SHARE SAVE ...

Arakan Times
Published on Nov

Ro Nay San Lwin

Like Share ...
2,488 Shares

476 Views · about a year ago · G

Chat (17)

RGA Collecting Workflow

RGAs Collecting Workflow

Cataloging

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Rohingya Archive ID	Source Platform	Offline Source Name	Uploader Display Name	Uploader User ID	Video ID	Upload Date	Upload Time
R000196	Twitter		Ro Nay San Lwin	nslwin	912378270909452288	2017-09-25	18:08:25 +0000
R000197	Twitter		Ro Nay San Lwin	nslwin	911906657684348928	2017-09-24	10:54:24 +0000
R000198	Twitter		Ro Nay San Lwin	nslwin	911904904045834246	2017-09-24	10:47:26 +0000
R000199	Twitter		Ro Nay San Lwin	nslwin	910804797699260416	2017-09-21	09:56:00 +0000
R000200	Twitter		Ro Nay San Lwin	nslwin	910029593448501248	2017-09-19	06:35:37 +0000
R000201	Twitter		Ro Nay San Lwin	nslwin	909079814627299328	2017-09-16	15:41:32 +0000
R000202	Twitter		Ro Nay San Lwin	nslwin	908980755300265984	2017-09-16	09:07:54 +0000
R000203	Twitter		Ro Nay San Lwin	nslwin	908243792041562112	2017-09-14	08:19:29 +0000
R000204	Twitter		Ro Nay San Lwin	nslwin	907562562535002118	2017-09-12	11:12:31 +0000
R000205	Twitter		Ro Nay San Lwin	nslwin	907516550768361472	2017-09-12	08:09:41 +0000

Where we're at now

- Policies, workflows and data dictionary are documented.
- Continuing to build collection.
- Exploring how collection can be used in investigative, accountability, and justice efforts.
- Exploring how the collection can be made accessible to Rohingya community as a resource.
- Exploring how to make workflow documentation accessible for others to use.

Needs / Gaps

- For the most part, tools exist, but not all easy to use, or not all open source.
 - GUIs for existing media + metadata collection tools and easy step-by-step guidance and/or recipes.
 - Open source alternatives, e.g. to FileMaker [?]
- WhatsApp metadata, strategies for collecting from closed networks.
- Easy data modeling tools and walkthrough resources.
- Identifying duplicate content across different format/files.

Thanks!

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